

HORIZON JU Research and Innovation Actions
HORIZON-EUROHPC-JU-2021-COE-01-01
European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking

Plasma Exascale-Performance Simulations CoE
101093261

D1.13

Updated assessment of developments and revision of scientific challenge - Predicting Near-Earth Space Dynamics with Vlasiator

WP1: Plasma Simulations - Codes and Grand Challenges

Date of preparation (latest version): 30/06/2025
Copyright© 2023 – 2027 The Plasma-PEPSC Consortium

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable Number	D1.13
Deliverable Name	Updated assessment of developments and revision of scientific challenge - Predicting Near-Earth Space Dynamics with Vlasiator
Due Date	30/06/2025
Deliverable lead	UoH
Authors	Urs Ganse (UoH), Markus Battarbee (UoH), Leo Kotipalo (UoH) and Markku Alho (UoH)
Responsible Author	Urs Ganse (UoH) E-mail: urs.ganse@helsinki.fi
Keywords	Plasma simulation, Vlasov equation, mesh refinement, sparse grids, profiling, performance extrapolation
WP/Task	WP1/Task D1.13
Nature	R
Dissemination Level	PU
Final Version Date	30/06/2025
Reviewed by	Vassilis Papaefstathiou (FORTH) & Valentin Seitz (BSC)

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Partner	Date	Comment	Version
UoH	23/05/2025	First draft, introduction and code description	0.1
UoH	28/05/2025	Development summary and updated gap analysis	0.2
UoH	02/06/2025	Roadmap, summaries and internal proofreading	0.2.1
UoH	03/06/2025	Introduction and conclusion	0.2.2
UoH	03/06/2025	Final draft ready for internal review	0.3
KTH	04/06/2025	Final draft updated for internal review	0.4
UoH	17/06/2025	Revised draft after internal review	0.5
KTH	23/06/2023	Final cleanup for submission	1.0

Executive Summary

In this deliverable, we provide an update of the progress for the Vlasiator plasma simulation code, in terms of its development progress towards the scientific target case within Plasma-PEPSC. It gives an outline of the basic physical environment and state of the art of near-Earth plasma simulations that Vlasiator performs, and reiterates the scientific target case which would be desirable to simulate within the timeframe of this EuroHPC project. Performance profiling results of Vlasiator have been updated at various scales, and their results are being presented, in direct comparison to the earlier results from deliverable D1.4 [1].

Based on the profiling data, performance extrapolation to the scientific target case shows that Vlasiator currently has a performance gap of a factor 32 compared to what would be required, down from the initial gap value of 52 at the beginning of the project. We discuss further steps in the development of the simulation code to address this gap, and give an overview of the planned improvements to the code.

Contents

1	Introduction	6
2	Background and Scientific Challenge	6
3	Summary of developments	8
3.1	GPU porting	8
3.1.1	Memory management and architectural improvements	9
3.1.2	Vlasov solver porting	9
3.1.3	Block adjustment	10
3.1.4	Initialisation and data reductions	10
3.1.5	Unified codebase for CUDA and HIP/ROCm	11
3.1.6	Field solver	11
3.1.7	Ionosphere solver	11
3.2	Non-global timestepping	11
3.3	Load balancing advancements	12
3.4	MPI optimisations based on benchmarking insights	13
4	Results: Revision of Gap analysis	14
4.1	Roadmap	16
5	Related Work	17
6	Conclusion	17

1 Introduction

Vlasiator[2, 3] is a kinetic plasma simulation system designed and focused on simulation of the near-Earth space environment. Its scientific goal is to simulate the plasma processes in and around Earth’s Magnetosphere on ion-kinetic scales, to serve both as a fundamental physics laboratory and work in tandem with spacecraft instrument design and data analysis efforts from national and international space agencies.

2 Background and Scientific Challenge

Figure 1: Example of a high-resolution magnetosphere simulation output from Vlasiator: Earth, in the centre, generates its magnetic dipole field (field lines are shown in purple), which gets deformed and shaped by the arriving solar wind from the sun (off the right in this figure). The plotted colourmap shows the plasma temperature, as it gets heated by the bow shock and kinetic plasma phenomena.

The specific scientific challenge that the Vlasiator team is working towards is a complete, three-dimensional modeling run of Earth’s entire magnetosphere at resolutions that correspond to ion kinetic scales. In Deliverable D1.4 [1] at the start of the Plasma-PEPSC project, we formulated the concrete requirements for our target case, quoted here verbatim from that document:

- A simulation of global coupling of Solar Wind↔Magnetosphere↔Ionosphere in a simulation box that contains part of the solar wind and extends to at least $-100 R_E$ in the tail. The overall physical size of the simulation box directly correlates with the computational intensity of a simulation.

- The inner simulation boundary should be located at $2.5 R_E$ (or further in). As the magnetic field strength of Earth’s dipole field rises sharply close to Earth ($B \sim r^{-3}$), this creates a numerical challenge: The plasma’s Larmor frequency $\Omega = \frac{q_i B}{m_i}$ needs to be resolved by the simulation timestep. Thus, this parameter affects computational scaling by a factor of $1/x^3$.
- Spatial resolution of the simulation mesh (at the highest refinement level) should be 500 km or finer. This means one additional refinement level compared to the current top-end Vlasiator simulations, and a factor of 8 more field solver cells.
- The run should continue for at least two simulated hours, about four times as long as the current record.
- As opposed to the current homogeneous solar wind inflow conditions, the inflowing solar wind conditions should be time-varying (representing realistic solar wind transient effects, like turbulent CME sheath regions or flux ropes).
- The outer size of the simulation domain should be chosen so that it includes Earth’s wave foreshock structure, with its spatially varying and complex structure of velocity distribution functions.
- We want to be able to automatically make decisions about dynamic mesh refinement and subgrid modeling at run-time, in order to track the physical phenomena of interest with maximum possible fidelity.

At the start of the Plasma-PEPSC project, we identified that all required simulation components and solvers are in place: A suitable ionosphere model [4], adaptive mesh refinement of the spatial grid [3], an appropriately low-diffusivity semilagrangian Vlasov solver [5]. However, the interplay of these components was not fine-tuned, and overall performance made the computational requirements for this scientific goal seem out of reach. The initial gap analysis per D1.4 was determined on the assumption that a realistic large computing grant on an exascale machine (corresponding to half of the machine’s resources for a month) should be sufficient to run the target case. At that point, this corresponded to 800 nodes of LUMI-C. The performance gap for Vlasiator is thus calculated by estimating the extrapolated computational cost of the science case on 800 nodes of LUMI-C, and dividing it by 80 million core-hours:

$$\text{GAP} = \frac{(\Delta t_{\text{Vlasov}} + \Delta t_{\text{Fields}}) \times n_{\text{timesteps}}}{80 \times 10^6 \text{ core-hours}}. \quad (1)$$

In D1.4, the target case’s numerical properties were specified in terms of concrete numbers of simulation spatial grid cells, fieldsolver grid cells, velocity distribution function (VDF) cells and total simulated physical time. In Table 1, we compare these numbers with the current maximum values actually obtained in simulation runs. Note that these are from distinct runs: The longest simulation currently conducted had a much lower spatial resolution, and hence cell count, than the actual high-fidelity science runs. Together, these runs have demonstrated that Vlasiator solvers have the required numerical stability and resolution capability for performing the target case science run.

Quantity	Target case	Recent prod. runs	Fulfilled?
Spatial grid cells	5.56×10^7	2.26×10^7	Almost
Fieldsolver cells	4.48×10^9	4.71×10^8	No
VDF cells	4.61×10^{12}	4.69×10^{12}	Yes
Physical run time	> 2 hours	2h 46min	Yes

Table 1: Comparison of Vlasiator target case numerical quantities as determined in D1.4 with most recent Vlasiator run results.

3 Summary of developments

Vlasiator development in the last two years focused primarily on three large refactoring approaches to gain effective performance on current HPC architectures: Porting of Vlasiator to GPUs (with complete data residency in GPU memory), removal of the global timestep constraints and new algorithms for load balancing. Each of these are outlined below.

The fully run-time adaptive mesh refinement of Vlasiator, published in [6], has now been taken into use in production. Maximum resolution is now adaptively following the physics of the simulation, and coarser cells are employed in spots with less scientific interest, freeing up resources dynamically. While this does not effect any measured change in the performance numbers as a function of cell count, like the FOM calculations stipulate, it does provide a significant step towards the target science case, as the required numbers of Vlasov grid cells are significantly reduced for the same physical fidelity.

Vlasiator’s code development practices continue to evolve, finding inspiration and support from the other consortium partners. Vlasiator’s primary git repository now performs automatic testing for continuous integration (CI) based on Github actions, with runners hosted on the local cluster of the University of Helsinki (hardware provided courtesy of the Finnish Grid and Cloud Initiative, FGCI) and the HCA cluster at Barcelona Supercomputing Centre. Code review meetings and integration-focused “merge days” have become central to the development progress.

In addition, a multitude of small performance micro-optimisations and removal of individual performance hot spots have been performed.

3.1 GPU porting

A GPU-compatible port of Vlasiator has been envisioned since the late 2010s, with preliminary work towards directive-based OpenACC porting taking place in 2019 and 2020. A dedicated push towards porting critical functionality of Vlasiator to CUDA and HIP/ROCm has been underway since the beginning of 2021. Due to the object-oriented programming approach and non-uniform non-constant grid structures of Vlasiator and the way the physical solvers interact, much effort was required in preparatory and groundbreaking work, in order to facilitate the required operations to take place on GPU hardware. In particular during the first 30 months of Plasma-PEPSC, this work has come to fruition.

3.1.1 Memory management and architectural improvements

Vlasiator utilizes a sparse velocity space [5] where for each spatial cell, the size and shape of the modeled and stored region of phase-space is adjusted several times per time step. This is crucial for being able to fit the physical problem into memory, with sparsity accounting for over 99% of savings in memory. As such, when acting upon a spatial cell (represented by an object with various data containers), the sizes of these containers can vary from cell to cell and from timestep to timestep. Consequently, information of these cell objects needs to be retained both on-device (for the computational kernels to be able to adjust and update the relevant information) and on the host (for the program to be able to define suitable launch parameters for computational kernels). A crucial piece to the puzzle of being able to manage these containers both on host and on device was the in-house development of the portable unified memory vector and hash map constructs [7]. These are built to support both CUDA and HIP/ROCm and allow the correct data to be accessible at all times from both host and device sides.

During the winter of 2024–2025, an approach was finalised which allows crucial data to remain in unified memory but reside as only paged to device during regular operations. Host-side copies or cached counters are used for kernel launch parameters, and these values are carefully maintained as up-to-date. As the data still resides in unified memory, it is trivial to perform sanity checks between cached and actual values. This caching approach was crucial in preventing the memory subsystem from paging this unified memory data between the host and the device. Paging of data back and forth has a significant detrimental effect on performance.

3.1.2 Vlasov solver porting

As of spring 2025, the computationally intensive portions of the Vlasov solvers of Vlasiator act on data residing in either device memory or unified memory which does not need paging to host. As such, the basic performance criteria for on-device computation are fulfilled.

The translation solver (spatial propagation) has been optimised and kernel merging has been performed, so that for each Cartesian translation direction there is only a single kernel launch which processes the whole necessary data, utilising pre-allocated temporary buffers for the Vlasov remapping. There are still some remaining optimisations pending, such as implementing more fused multiply-add (FMA) instructions. Also, the current memory access patterns suffer from significant long scoreboard stalls, a topic for future investigation and optimisation, as the reason for this is not yet known. The translation solver is, however, well-optimised in comparison with other portions, and has been in a relatively stable state.

The semi-Lagrangian acceleration solver (based on the SLICE-3D approach of [8]) was ported to a CUDA kernel as early as January 2023. Many of the auxiliary tasks of preparing data for acceleration were ported piece-by-piece, but the legacy of serial CPU operations was still present for a long time. During the spring of 2025, the rest of the acceleration solver has been re-designed with more compact kernels which utilise best practices of GPU programming and will facilitate increased parallelism. This re-writing is still underway at the time of this report. A crucial step in this task was actually re-designing the algorithms for parallel operations. For example, instead of utilising a CPU or GPU

sorting call (CUDA `cuda::DeviceRadixSort` or ROCm `hipcub::DeviceRadixSort`) to build a list of objects to process according to Cartesian direction, a probe cube filling algorithm was instead devised allowing for rapid parallel reduction and scan operations. In addition, utilisation of custom-built kernels is more flexible in allowing for parallel evaluation of several different spatial cells, something which is not supported in, e.g., industry-standard sort libraries.

A fully parallelised acceleration Vlasov solver is envisioned to be operational in June 2025, with improved memory management allowing for further parallelism added in August. At this point, the Vlasov solvers are expected to surpass the CPU branch in performance, allowing a first GPU-supported release of the Vlasiator codebase, along with implementation of automated continuous integration using GPUs.

3.1.3 Block adjustment

As previously highlighted, the Vlasiator memory management system requires constant and repetitive re-adjustment of managed velocity space. This *Block adjustment* was implemented in a completely serial approach on CPUs, necessitating a complete algorithmic re-design of the block adjustment methodology. This was successfully implemented, presented and benchmarked in the first Vlasiator GPU architectural publication [9]. This block adjustment refactoring work was crucial in facilitating a sample test simulation showcasing $3\times$ speed improvements of 1 NVIDIA A100 GPU (orchestrated by 32 CPU cores / threads / streams) compared against 32 similar CPU cores, as reported in [9].

3.1.4 Initialisation and data reductions

During the fall of 2024, the initialisation of Vlasiator data structures was ported to GPUs utilising our in-house flexible ARCH-looping interface, minimising codebase divergence between CPU and GPU implementations. It should be noted that in its current implementation, the ARCH looping interface is not yet suitable for performance-critical tasks, and as such, more frequent data reductions such as plasma moment calculations are currently implemented with dedicated kernels. For once-off actions such as initialisation or more infrequent tasks such as building in-situ data reduction for disk output, this is a successful and sufficient method already in its current form.

During the fall of 2023, distribution function initialisation, memory buffer allocation, file I/O, checkpointing and restarting, and certain MPI-communication features of the translation solver were improved drastically. Significant improvements were achieved by utilising and re-using pre-allocated padded memory buffers as much as possible.

Despite transitioning to device-side operations, utilising unified memory prefetching and multiple streams, GPU performance remains at levels which cannot be applied to global runs. This is partly due to memory slowdowns resulting from prefetching and/or page faulting within the unified memory subsystem. Another contributing factor is that the column construction and block adjustment algorithms, despite having been rewritten to be performed by kernels, are still somewhat sequential in nature. Although they have been somewhat parallelised, they may rely strongly on atomic operations which may cause stalling of the system. Further optimisation with the specific goal of tackling these slowdowns is planned.

3.1.5 Unified codebase for CUDA and HIP/ROCm

In June of 2023, the applicability of our CUDA / HIP/ROCm approach was validated, when Vlasiator was successfully ran on LUMI-G with 8 MPI tasks, each with 7 CPU threads equaling 7 GPU streams, with minor adjustments after automatic conversion from CUDA to HIP code. Later during the summer, the codebase was refactored into utilising compiler directives. In our approach, a single unified codebase, with generalised GPU macros, is re-defined into CUDA or HIP calls by the compiler pre-processor, as requested by user-defined flags. This approach, implemented already in 2023, continues to be successful.

3.1.6 Field solver

Investigations into the data access patterns of Vlasiator’s field solver during 2023–2024 uncovered a number of legacy code limitations. As such, the Vlasiator team has leveraged their continued efficient collaboration with the Finnish supercomputing centre CSC – IT CENTER FOR SCIENCE LTD. with experienced developers from CSC taking lead on a complete re-write of the Vlasiator field data container FSgrid. The newly formulated FSgrid library has not yet been merged into the Vlasiator development branch but is operational, undergoing final adjustments to interfaces. This approach will facilitate the implementation of a portable parallel interface for FSgrid which will be able to utilise GPU hardware as well as CPU threads.

3.1.7 Ionosphere solver

The Vlasiator ionospheric potential solver has continued development in 2024–2025[4], which has postponed implementation of a GPU version. The computational cost of the ionospheric solver is minimal in comparison with the Vlasov solvers, so this has been an acceptable state. However, during this development, it was found that existing state-of-the-art linear algebra libraries such as Eigen [10] were in fact superior to the legacy solver employed in the Vlasiator ionosphere, and as such, switching over to a standard interface for the solver will allow for an easy plug-in-approach in switching to GPU-accelerated solvers where requested.

3.2 Non-global timestepping

Non-global timestepping (timeclasses) refers to a spatially-varying timestepping scheme for the Vlasov solver, where the domain is decomposed to regions according to cell-wise constraints on timestepping. This is especially important near the inner boundary, where the magnetic field magnitude rises sharply ($\propto r^{-3}$), driving the otherwise-global timestep down precipitously. The implementation of timeclasses has required significant refactoring of the DCCRG grid library (neighborhood stencil search reorganisation) and new approaches to MPI communications (ghost translation), which were implemented by the end of 2024.

The Vlasov timeclass solver now has a functioning prototype, running the acceleration, translation and field solvers in conjunction, and integration testing of the solver

components is underway, as well as the rebasing of the timeclass solvers to the newly-introduced GPU capabilities. Ideally, with the current timestep refinement ratio of 2, the timeclass solvers would provide a speedup of approximately $4\text{--}5\times$ for the current production runs with the inner boundary at $4.7 R_E$, and would mitigate the increase in computational effort caused by global timestepping when pushing the inner boundary inwards. However, synchronising the semi-Lagrangian remapping operator across different timeclasses will introduce overhead in the form of VDF halo regions on the order of Vlasov translation stencil width at the timeclass interfaces. This will somewhat impact the potential speedup, which can be partially mitigated by e.g. optimising the timeclass region allocation to avoid small patches of mismatching timeclasses or by investigating using larger timestep refinement ratios, which may be required close to the inner boundary below $4 R_E$ due to sharp gradient in timeclass requirements: Inner boundary at $2 R_E$ already suggests a timestep range varying by a factor of 1000. Further, the load balancing act on the timeclassified solvers will be nontrivial, especially as this will decouple the computational effort from the memory footprint.

3.3 Load balancing advancements

Figure 2: Spatial maps of the load balancing partitioning of a Vlasiator magnetospheric simulation, using different algorithms provided by the Zoltan library. Equal-colour patches correspond to parts of the simulation domain handled by a single MPI rank.

An investigation of the Zoltan library’s [11] load balancing algorithms was conducted on a large-scale Vlasiator run on LUMI. Figure 2 shows examples of the spatial partitioning created by these algorithms, showing that they differ significantly in the resulting subdomain geometries. Box plots of propagation times for the five algorithms tested are shown in Figure 3. The findings correlated well with initial results from deliverable D3.2 [12], with the method of Hilbert space-filling curves (HSFC) outperforming the previous choice of recursive inertial bisection (RIB) by about 4%. These gains were mainly in spatial propagation, which is the largest component of propagation time overall.

HSFC optimisation, also presented in deliverable D3.2 [12], was continued further. In addition to curves tested earlier, we implemented the hyperorthogonal curves *Alfa* and *Beta* into Zoltan. These are identified by Haverkort [13] as the curves with optimal locality according to different metrics; this reduces communication overhead for spatial propagation. Box plots of propagation times for the eight curves tested are shown in Figure 4. We found an improvement of about 1% for the Beta curve over Zoltan’s existing Hilbert curve implementation, while other tested curves seemed to perform worse. The

Figure 3: Box plots of total (a) and spatial (b) propagation time for the five algorithms evaluated.

differences are mainly in spatial propagation. All curves tested were merged into Zoltan on the Trilinos project's `develop` branch.

Figure 4: Box plots of total (a) and spatial (b) propagation time for the eight curves evaluated.

These findings are presented in more detail in a recently submitted manuscript, the preprint of which is available on arXiv [14].

3.4 MPI optimisations based on benchmarking insights

In close collaboration with Barcelona Supercomputing Centre through the POP project, a number of realistic benchmarking runs of Vlsiator were run on the MareNostrum5 machine, scaling up to 500 CPU nodes of the machine, while instrumented with BSC's `extrae` / `paraver` toolset [15, 16, 17]. The resulting performance analysis revealed a number of MPI performance bottlenecks that the Vlsiator team had suspected, but not before been able to pinpoint and resolve.

A thorough analysis of these profiling results, proposed improvements and performance benefits will be published in a proceedings paper of the third EuroHPC user day [18].

4 Results: Revision of Gap analysis

To update the performance evaluation and gap analysis of Vlasiator, we have taken performance data from the most recent production-scale Vlasiator runs on LUMI-C (performed during the MICK, FEMMA and KHALEESSI grants).

During runtime, Vlasiator continuously reports profiling statistics using its built-in, lightweight phiprof[19] library. The numbers obtained are thus directly representative of a current, large-scale magnetosphere simulation run in its realistic production environment and can be scaled directly to the target case.

The Vlasiator figure of merit (FOM) has been defined in two distinct ways:

1. In the Plasma-PEPSC grant agreement (GA), we defined a hardware-independent dimensionless quantity (smaller is better) based on cell updates and aggregate memory bandwidth:

$$\text{FOM}_{\text{GA}} = \text{time per timestep [s]} \times \frac{\text{memory bandwidth [B/s]}}{\text{bytes to propagate [B]}} \quad (2)$$

2. In deliverable D1.4 [1], this number was re-asserted to be a weak-scaling criterion (larger is better):

$$\text{FOM}_{\text{D1.4}} = \frac{\text{phase space cells/s}}{\text{memory bandwidth [MB/s]}} \quad (3)$$

The reader is advised to note the inverse relationship between these two definitions.

Furthermore, these figures were calculated independently for the Vlasov solver (FOM_{V}) and field solver (FOM_{F}), as their scaling properties are distinct. For performance extrapolation to the target case, both solvers' behaviour is scaled independently and the total timestep taken into account, compare Eq. 1.

In extension of Table 2 from deliverable D1.4 [1], the cell counts and resulting simulation FOM values have been updated and are presented as Table 2. Figures 5 and 6 present the same information graphically. The scaling behaviour of the Vlasov solver has proven itself to be satisfactory, in that it does manage to retain the $\text{FOM}_{\text{V}} < 1000$ target throughout the whole scale regime up to our target case. The field solver in its current form, however, appears to have hit a scaling barrier around 10^9 field solver cells, going clearly above $\text{FOM}_{\text{F}} > 1000$ in all recent production runs. This affects our planned development focus in the near future, see section 4.1 below.

As the Vlasov solver cell counts has now already reached the target case estimate, we are directly scaling our computational requirement estimates using the same Vlasov timestep size Δt_{Vlasov} . The field solver, with its currently still less advantageous scaling behaviour, has its timestep value Δt_{Field} linearly extrapolated to the target scale.

With these assumptions, the new Vlasiator gap value as of June 2025 is

$$\text{GAP} = 31.87 \quad (4)$$

Nodes	Machine	Phase space cells	Field solver cells	FOM _{D1.4} Vlasov	FOM _{D1.4} Fields	FOM _{GA} Vlasov	FOM _{GA} Fields
1	LUMI-C	4.63×10^8	100672	1.10×10^9	3.53×10^6	222.43	134.48
8	LUMI-C	6.27×10^9	41779200	2.04×10^9	2.02×10^6	108.6	234.87
50	Mahti	4.49×10^{10}	49836032	8.03×10^8	1.01×10^6	234.12	471.15
250	LUMI-C	5.77×10^{11}	5.55×10^8	6.29×10^8	2.36×10^5	391.57	2012.07
500	LUMI-C	1.30×10^{12}	4.71×10^8	3.11×10^{10}	1.13×10^7	443.01	2628.36
512	LUMI-C	4.73×10^{12}	2.61×10^8	7.70×10^{10}	1.91×10^7	204.41	1585.39

Table 2: Simulation phase space / fieldsolver cell sizes and figures of merit for the down-scaled target cases of Vlasiator global magnetospheric runs. The first four runs are an explicit scaling series from 1 to 250 nodes, whereas the last two are numbers taken from production-scale science runs.

Figure 5: Scaling graph and extrapolation of Vlasiator's figure of merit (FOM) calculated according to the calculation defined in D1.4 (eq. 3). The connected dots show a scaling test series from a single node up to 250 nodes on LUMI-C. The two additional data points show recent large-scale Vlasiator production runs on 500 and 512 nodes of LUMI-C, respectively. Scaling of Vlasov (purple) and field solvers (green) are shown separately, with their target case cell counts denoted by dashed vertical lines.

Figure 6: Scaling graph and extrapolation of Vlasiator’s figure of merit (FOM) calculated according to the calculation defined in the grant agreement (eq. 2). The data points and colours are identical to Figure 5. Additionally, the success criterion outlined in the GA (FOM < 1000) is drawn as a dashed horizontal line.

4.1 Roadmap

The next major steps in Vlasiator development consist of taking into production the recent advances outlined in section 3 above.

GPU support has been merged into the primary development branch, but appropriate resources for a GPU-based production run have not yet been obtained, as the scaling behaviour was still varying strongly during development. This will now be remedied. With proper GPU scaling data, quantitative decisions can be made whether to target the next production runs to GPU or CPU systems.

The non-global timestep implementation, is still in a prototype stage. It will require thorough testing and integration runs, before its performance impact at scale can be quantified. In any case, it will be a substantial step towards moving the simulation’s inner boundary further earthward. This process is expected to be completed throughout the year 2026.

Yet, the remaining gap value of 31.87 will not be sufficiently reduced by these two developments alone. As the scaling analysis in Section 4 demonstrates, the field solver presents a scaling barrier. Work on GPU porting of this component of the code is well underway (compare Section 3.1.6) and an advanced MPI partitioning scheme, in which only a subset of the participating compute nodes solve the Fields is already functional, but has not been tested at scale. In this problem, we are in exchange of ideas with the GENE and GENE-X development teams, which likewise focus on field solver scalability progress.

5 Related Work

As part of the collaborative effort that is the Plasma-PEPSC project, Vlasiator development happens in direct correspondence and interaction with the other consortium partners through the technical work packages (WP2–WP5). Consequently, the deliverables associated with these workpackages’ tasks contain more detailed technical information about the individual performance optimisation, benchmarking and consolidation work that has been performed.

Scientific analysis of the production-scale magnetospheric runs that were used in the scaling analysis is still ongoing. First publications based on their data have recently been published in [20, 21, 22].

6 Conclusion

Vlasiator’s performance development towards the exascale target case progresses as the Plasma-PEPSC project continues. The performance gap for the scientific target case has shrunk from 52 at the beginning of the progress to a new value of $GAP = 31.87$ as of June 2025.

Several large code refactoring steps have been completed, most prevalently efficient GPU support, non-global timestepping and significantly improved load balancing. These are being integrated, tested and benchmarked for production readiness.

Vlasiator has shown numerical solver stability for the required physical time duration and resolution of the target case.

Further developments are already ongoing, and the development appears to be on track to fulfill the target science case by the conclusion of the project.

References

- [1] Urs Ganse. Plasma-pepsc d1.4 initial definition of the scientific challenges and initial evaluation plan - predicting near-earth space dynamics with vlasiator, June 2023.
- [2] Minna Palmroth, Urs Ganse, Yann Pfau-Kempf, Markus Battarbee, Lucile Turc, Thiago Brito, Maxime Grandin, Sanni Hoilijoki, Arto Sandroos, and Sebastian von Alfthan. Vlasov methods in space physics and astrophysics. *Living Reviews in Computational Astrophysics*, 4(1):1, August 2018.
- [3] Urs Ganse, Tuomas Koskela, Markus Battarbee, Yann Pfau-Kempf, Konstantinos Papadakis, Markku Alho, Maarja Bussov, Giulia Cozzani, Maxime Dubart, Harriet George, Evgeny Gordeev, Maxime Grandin, Konstantinos Horaites, Jonas Suni, Vertti Tarvus, Fasil Tesema Kebede, Lucile Turc, Hongyang Zhou, and Minna Palmroth. Enabling technology for global 3d + 3v hybrid-vlasov simulations of near-earth space. *Physics of Plasmas*, 30(4):042902, April 2023.
- [4] Urs Ganse, Yann Pfau-Kempf, Hongyang Zhou, Liisa Juusola, Abiyot. Workayehu, Fasil Kebede, Konstantinos Papadakis, Maxime Grandin, Markku Alho, Markus Battarbee, Maxime Dubart, Leo Kotipalo, Arnaud Lalagüe, Jonas Suni, Konstantinos Horaites, and Minna Palmroth. The vlasiator 5.2 ionosphere – coupling a magnetospheric hybrid-vlasov simulation with a height-integrated ionosphere model. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 18(2):511–527, 2025.
- [5] S. von Alfthan, D. Pokhotelov, Y. Kempf, S. Hoilijoki, I. Honkonen, A. Sandroos, and M. Palmroth. Vlasiator: First global hybrid-vlasov simulations of earth’s foreshock and magnetosheath. *Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics*, 120(0):24 – 35, 2014.
- [6] Leo Kotipalo, Markus Battarbee, Yann Pfau-Kempf, and Minna Palmroth. Physics-motivated cell-octree adaptive mesh refinement in the vlasiator 5.3 global hybrid-vlasov code. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 17(16):6401–6413, 2024.
- [7] K. Papadakis, M. Battarbee, U. Ganse, Y. Pfau-Kempf, and M. Palmroth. Hashinator: A portable hybrid hashmap designed for heterogeneous high performance computing. *Frontiers in Computer Science*, 6, 2024.
- [8] M. Zerroukat and T. Allen. A three-dimensional monotone and conservative semi-lagrangian scheme (SLICE-3D) for transport problems. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 138(667):1640–1651, 2012.
- [9] Markus Battarbee, Konstantinos Papadakis, Urs Ganse, Jaro Hokkanen, Leo Kotipalo, Yann Pfau-Kempf, Markku Alho, and Minna Palmroth. Porting the grid-based 3d+3v hybrid-vlasov kinetic plasma simulation vlasiator to heterogeneous gpu architectures. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2997(1):012010, April 2025.
- [10] Gaël Guennebaud, Benoît Jacob, et al. Eigen v3. <http://eigen.tuxfamily.org>, 2010.

- [11] E. G. Boman, U. V. Catalyurek, C. Chevalier, and K. D. Devine. The Zoltan and Isorropia parallel toolkits for combinatorial scientific computing: Partitioning, ordering, and coloring. *Scientific Programming*, 20(2):129–150, 2012.
- [12] Martin Schulz, Jeremy Williams, Markus Battarbee, Leo Kotipalo, Felix Jung, Srikanth Sathyanarayana, Isaias Urena, and Tilman Dannert. Plasma-pepsc d3.2 updated report on mpi, load balancing and resilience in plasma codes, December 2024.
- [13] Herman Haverkort. How many three-dimensional hilbert curves are there? *Journal of Computational Geometry*, 8(1):206–281, 9 2017.
- [14] Leo Kotipalo, Markus Battarbee, Yann Pfau-Kempf, Vertti Tarvus, and Minna Palmroth. Load balancing in strongly inhomogeneous simulations – a vlasiator case study, 2025. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2505.20908>.
- [15] Michael Wagner, Stephan Mohr, Judit Giménez, and Jesús Labarta. A structured approach to performance analysis. In Christoph Niethammer, Michael M. Resch, Wolfgang E. Nagel, Holger Brunst, and Hartmut Mix, editors, *Tools for High Performance Computing 2017*, pages 1–15, Cham, 2019. Springer International Publishing.
- [16] Extrae Team. Extrae | BSC-Tools.
- [17] V. Pillet, J. Labarta, A. Cortes, and S. Girona. Paraver: A tool to visualize and analyze parallel code. In *World occam and Transputer User Group Technical Meeting*, page 17, 04 1995.
- [18] Valentin Seitz, Markus Battarbee, Urs Ganse, Vertti Tarvus, Minna Palmroth, and Marta Garcia-Gasulla. Performance analysis of vlasiator at production-scale. In *Proceedings of the Third EuroHPC user day*, 2025. submitted.
- [19] Sebastian von Alfthan. Phiprof – parallel hierarchical profiler. <https://github.com/fmihpc/hiprof>, 2023.
- [20] Lauri Pänkäläinen, Giulia Cozzani, Markus Battarbee, Urs Ganse, Yann Pfau-Kempf, Jonas Suni, and Minna Palmroth. Identifying magnetotail jet front signatures in a 3d + 3v global hybrid-vlasov simulation. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, 130(6), May 2025.
- [21] Giulia Cozzani, Markku Alho, Ivan Zaitsev, Hongyang Zhou, Sanni Hoilijoki, Lucile Turc, Maxime Grandin, Kosta Horaites, Markus Battarbee, Yann Pfau-Kempf, Urs Ganse, Kostis Papadakis, and Minna Palmroth. Interplay of magnetic reconnection and current sheet kink instability in the earth’s magnetotail. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 52(2), January 2025.
- [22] I. Zaitsev, G. Cozzani, M. Alho, K. Horaites, H. Zhou, A. Kit, Y. Pfau-Kempf, S. Hoilijoki, U. Ganse, M. Battarbee, K. Papadakis, J. Suni, M. Dubart, F. Tesema-Kebede, A. Workayehu, V. Tarvus, L. Kotipalo, V. Koikkalainen, L. Turc, and M. Palmroth. Ion-mediated tearing and kink instabilities in the earth’s magnetosphere: Hybrid-vlasov simulations. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, 130(1), January 2025.